

MORPHOLOGICAL FORMATION OF SPORTS TERMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *The article discusses about the fact that knowing the structural-morphological features of sports terminology and word formation models in foreign languages helps students to learn foreign languages perfectly and carefully. In addition, four criteria for classifying the lexicon related to sports terminology are shown: morphological structure, the number of components, and semantic features. In addition, information is provided about the formation of new words with the help of affixes, that is, derivation.*

Keywords: *sports terminology, Derivation, Morphological structure, Word formation, Suffixes, Prefixes.*

In the process of learning a foreign language, students and professionals are rapidly increasing their vocabulary. In addition, it is necessary not only to expand the vocabulary, but also to enrich it qualitatively, to develop the ability to actively use the existing vocabulary in any situation. The native speaker freely uses all the word formation tools and models of his native language, while the learner of a foreign language uses only the vocabulary he has acquired and rarely creates lexical units based on the rules of word formation. In this regard, mastering the word formation models and rules of a foreign language is one of the necessary conditions for successfully mastering the lexicon of the studied foreign language. It is faster and more effective to learn about the unique and subtle features of terms related to the field, to master the methods of word formation, and to increase vocabulary compared to memorizing a large number of words in detail. At the same time, it is possible to understand the content of an unfamiliar word or phrase, the pattern of word formation (prefix, suffix or infix) in the development of language instinct [1]. Today, there is a complete list of all sports in the world with their own lexical units and industry terms. It allows the learner to try to form certain lexical units independently (without referring to the dictionary) using the available word formation tools based on the scope of knowledge, to participate in the process of creating words or phrases. In addition, it turns learning a foreign language into an interesting creative process and increases the learner's motivation to learn a language.

Sports lexicon and terminology is not a newly studied topic in linguistics. As a result of the emergence of new sports, the content of the sports dictionary is constantly updated, different types of sports dictionaries are created (dictionaries containing lexical units in one, two or more languages)[2]. The content of the sports lexicon is very diverse. Firstly, this is a lexicon in general use (it is understandable to all native speakers and is actively used by them in everyday life), secondly, it is professional terminology, thirdly, it is understandable only to a narrow circle of people who practice this sport.

During the research, we were convinced that the classification of the lexicon related to sports terminology is based on four criteria: morphological structure, the number of components, and semantic features. Before analyzing sports terminology morphologically, we found it

necessary to study sports terms by structurally dividing them into term-word and term-word combinations. Initially, it was decided to research the term-word lexical units related to sports (their share in sports terminology is 45%) from the point of view of morphological structure, separating simple (50%), artificial (37%) and complex lexical units (13%). Simple lexical units are lexical units with a single morpheme. For example: **ball** – *koptok*, **king** – *qirol*, **queen** – *qirolicha*, **bishop** – *fil* (*chess piece*), **side** – *maydonning biron tomoni*, **cue** – *kiy* (*the name of the cue stick used in snooker, billiard sports*), **fin** – *suzgich, final*, **back** – *bel*, **punt** – *to'pni urish harakati*, **blade** – *pichoq*, **deck** – *paluba*, **star** – *yulduz* (*a famous athlete*), **start** – *boshlamoq*, **float** – *suzmoq*, **handle** – *tutqich*, **ski** – *chang'i*, **drag** – *tashimoq*, **judge** – *hakam*, **lap** – *aylana*, **glove** – *go'lqop*, **coach** – *murabbiy*, **centre** – *markaz*, **wall** – *devor* (*obstacle*), **target** – *marra* (*target*), **basket** – *savat* (*basketball*), **guard** – *himoya*, **game** – *o'yin*, **ring** – *ring*, **line** – *maydonning biron chizig'i*, **skates** – *chang'i*, **soccer** – *futbol*, **chess** – *shahmat*, **team** – *jamoat*, **final** – *final*, **score** – *hisob*, **archer** – *kamonchi*, **golf** – *golf*, **weight** – *og'irlik*, **puck** – *shayba* (*hockey*), **cricket** – *kriket*, **dive** – *sho'ng'imoq* (*swimming*). When we classified sports terms according to their belonging to word groups, we saw that most of these lexemes belong to the noun group (92%). In addition, the following nouns, which grammatically belong to the noun group, are always used in the plural form. For example: **doors** – *darvozalar*, **boards** – *tomonlar*, **corners** – *burchaklar*, **laces** – *bog'ichlar*, **pants** – *reytuz* (*tor, sirma, yopishib turadigan shim*), **shorts** – *shortiklar, kalta ishtonlar*, **socks** – *getralar, paypoqlar*. The rest is 8%.

The next turn is artificial terms and lexemes. According to T.I. Vendina, the interrelation of basic and artificial words in the vocabulary of any language allows to understand the interests of people in different fields [3]. It is not an exaggeration to say that the role of multi-component terms and lexemes in the terminology of any field is incomparable. Their emergence is related to the fact that they are used in a certain field and the need to define new concepts that are logically based on already accepted concepts. In terms of form, the new term is usually related to the term representing the basic essence, the basic term is introduced as a component of the new term. Thus, we consider it reasonable that the new term was formed in a fundamental and formal-structural sense. Derivation is the creation of a new word using affixes (*sport - sportchi*). Derivation is a phenomenon of secondary formation. As a result of derivation, new units enter into various paradigmatic relations with other units of the language system. For the term, this phenomenon first forms a logical relationship [4]. Derivatives and basic terms in one terminological system have a logical relationship, therefore, they are formally related. Thus, the derivative relations of the new unit and the original unit can be considered as unique paradigmatic. If the units of two languages have a common element in terms of form and semantics, one of them is closely related to the other [5].

Lexical units related to the field of sports made by means of suffixes. In this method, suffixes -ing, -ion, -er/-or are productive in word formation. For example:

-ing: *dribbling* – *dribling*, *running* – *yugurish*, *bowling* – *bovling*, *autoracing* – *avtopoyga*, *diving* – *suva sho'ng'ish*, *yachting* – *yelkanli sport*, *jumping* – *uzoqlikka sakrash*, *boxing* – *boks*, *mountaineering* – *toqqa tirmashib chiqish*, *canoeing* – *kanoeda suzish*, *armwrestling* – *armrestling*, *qo'l jangi*, *training* – *shug'ullanmoq*, *fencing* – *qilichbozlik*, *ice-skating* – *muzda figurali uchish*, *fighting* – *kurash, jang qilish*.

-ion: *competition* – *musoboqa*, *champion* – *chempion*, *substitution* – *o'yinchi almashinuvi*, *suspension* – *diskvalifikatsiya*, *intermission* – *muzni ta'mirlash uchun xokkeyda*

berilgan tanaffus, **abstraction** – to'siq, **rotation** – rotatsiya (o'yinchining o'rnini almashtirish), **navigation** – navigatsiya.

-er/-or: **kicker** – to'pni tepuvchi, **flipper** – oyoq uchun rezina suzg'ich, **diver** – g'avvos, **runner** – yuguruvchi, **header** – boshqaruvchi (futbolda jamoa boshlig'i), **batter** – zarbani qaytaruvchi (beysbol), **bowler** – bouldingchi, **server** – sportchiga xizmat ko'rsatuvchi, **climber** – toqqa tirmashib chiquvchi (alpinist), **leader** – musoboqadagi yetakchi, **attacker** – hujumchi, **neck and throat protector** – iyak va tomoq himoya vositasi (xokkey).

From the given examples, we can see that terms and lexemes formed with the additions -ing, -ion, -er/-or are productive in English word formation. Below, we found it necessary to mention the additions that are not productive when making words related to the field of sports. These additions are – **ist:** **cyclist** – velosipedchi, **canoeist** – kanoechi (eshkak eshish sporti bilan shug'ullanuvchi), **judoist** – dzyudochi, **alpinist** – alpinist; **-ship:** **championship** – chempionat, **membership** – a'zolik, **friendship** – do'stlik; **-ment:** **equipment** – anjom, **placement** – joylashuv o'rni, **movement** – harakatlanish; **-ee:** **referee** – hakam; **absentee** – biron bir sabab bilan jamoa tarkibida bo'lmagan o'yinchi; **-ance:** **appearance** – paydo bo'lish, **make an appearance** – muz maydonida paydo bo'lmoq, o'yin maydoniga chiqmoq, **attendance** – jamoaning musobaqada qatnashuvi.

2. Lexical units related to the field of sports made by means of prefixes. For example: **out-** – **outsprint** – sprint yugurishida o'zib ketmoq, **outplay** – o'yinda g'alaba qozonmoq, **outclass** – ustunlikka ega bo'lmoq; **over-** – **overjump** – sakrab o'tmoq, **overhand** – to'pni qo'ldan tepada oshirib uzatish, **overall** – mutlaq, absolyut, **overtime** – qo'shimcha vaqt; **up-** – **upright** – darvoza to'sini; **inter-** – **interchange** – o'yinchilarning almashinuvi; **mid-** – **midfielder** – yarim himoyachi, **midgame** – o'yinning yarmi, musobaqaning yarmi; **dis-** – **dismount** – (otdan) tushmoq; **fore-** – **forecheck** (to check an opponent in ice hockey in the opponent's defensive zone) – xokkeyda himoyaga asoslangan o'yin; **back-** – **backcourt** – himoya maydoni (basketbol), **backhand** – chapdan berilgan zarba (tennis); **under-** – **undergrasp** – pastdan tutib olish; **mis-** – **miscue** – mo'ljaldan adashmoq.

3. In addition to the above two ways of word formation, there are also sports terms and lexemes made of unusual prefixes and suffixes. Below, we consider it necessary to give the following examples of terms and lexemes related to the field of sports made by means of prefixes and suffixes. For example: **infighting** – kurash, bellashuv, jang, **outsider** – autsayder (musobaqada) eng orqada qolgan o'yinchi yoki jamoa), **outfielder** – autfielder, himoyachi, maydon o'yinchisi (futbol), **all-rounder** – ko'p kurashchi, o'n kurashchi.

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